

THE IMPORTANT FUNCTION AND FORMATION OF CELLS IN HUMAN BODY

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Annotation: The article deals with the latest information about significant function of cells in the human body and their basic types. In addition to this, main functions of human cells were highlighted.

Key words: *cytoplasm enclosed, living organism, self-replicating, Trusted Source cells, Robert Hooke, monasteries, eukaryotic cells, prokaryotic cells, nucleoid region.*

The cell is the basic structural and functional unit of all forms of life. Every cell consists of cytoplasm enclosed within a membrane; many cells contain organelles, each with a specific function. The term comes from the Latin word *cellula* meaning 'small room'. Most cells are only visible under a microscope. Cells emerged on Earth about 4 billion years ago. All cells are capable of replication, protein synthesis, and motility. A cell is the smallest living organism and the basic unit of life on earth. Together, trillions of cells make up the human body. Cells have three parts: the membrane, the nucleus, and the cytoplasm. People can think of cells as tiny packages that contain minute factories, warehouses, transport systems, and power plants. They function on their own, creating their own energy and self-replicating — the cell is the smallest unit of life that can replicate. Cells are the basic units of life. The body contains around 50—100 trillion Trusted Source cells, and they vary widely in size, number, structure, and use.

Cells also communicate with each other. Whether in plants, humans, or animals, they connect to create a solid, well formed organism. In humans, cells

build tissues, tissues form organs, and organs work together to keep the body alive. Robert Hooke first discovered cells in the 1600s. He gave them their name because they resembled the “cella,” the Latin term for “small rooms” where monks lived in monasteries. Experts estimate that there are around 200 Trusted Source cell types in the human body. Cell types can look different, and carry out distinct roles within the body. For instance, a sperm cell resembles a tadpole, a female egg cell is spherical, and nerve cells are essentially thin tubes[1]. Cells are broadly categorized into two types: eukaryotic cells, which possess a nucleus, and prokaryotic cells, which lack a nucleus but have a nucleoid region. Prokaryotes are single-celled organisms, whereas eukaryotes can be either single-celled or multicellular.

Prokaryotes include bacteria and archaea, two of the three domains of life. Prokaryotic cells were the first form of life on Earth, characterized by having vital biological processes including cell signaling. They are simpler and smaller than eukaryotic cells, and lack a nucleus, and other membrane-bound organelles. The DNA of a prokaryotic cell consists of a single circular chromosome that is in direct contact with the cytoplasm. The nuclear region in the cytoplasm is called the nucleoid. Most prokaryotes are the smallest of all organisms, ranging from 0.5 to 2.0 μm in diameter. Plants, animals, fungi, slime moulds, protozoa, and algae are all eukaryotic. These cells are about fifteen times wider than a typical prokaryote and can be as much as a thousand times greater in volume. The main distinguishing feature of eukaryotes as compared to prokaryotes is compartmentalization: the presence of membrane-bound organelles (compartments) in which specific activities take place. Most important among these is a cell nucleus, an organelle that houses the cell's DNA. This nucleus gives the eukaryote its name, which means "true kernel (nucleus)".

The plasma membrane resembles that of prokaryotes in function, with minor differences in the setup. Cell walls may or may not be present. The eukaryotic DNA is organized in one or more linear molecules, called chromosomes, which are

associated with histone proteins. All chromosomal DNA is stored in the cell nucleus, separated from the cytoplasm by a membrane. Some eukaryotic organelles such as mitochondria also contain some DNA. Many eukaryotic cells are ciliated with primary cilia. Primary cilia play important roles in chemosensation, mechanosensation, and thermosensation. Each cilium may thus be "viewed as a sensory cellular antennae that coordinates a large number of cellular signaling pathways, sometimes coupling the signaling to ciliary motility or alternatively to cell division and differentiation." [2]. Motile eukaryotes can move using motile cilia or flagella. Motile cells are absent in conifers and flowering plants. Eukaryotic flagella are more complex than those of prokaryotes [3]. Despite their differences, cells often share certain structures. Red blood cells, most white blood cells, and platelets are produced in the bone marrow. However, 2 types of white blood cells—T cells and B cells (lymphocytes)—are also produced in the lymph nodes and spleen. T cells are also produced and mature in the thymus gland. Within the bone marrow, all blood cells originate from a single type of unspecialized cell called a stem cell. When a stem cell divides, it first becomes an immature red blood cell, white blood cell, or platelet-producing cell. The immature cell then divides, matures further, and ultimately becomes a mature red blood cell, white blood cell, or platelet.

The rate of blood cell production is controlled by the body's needs. Normal blood cells last for a limited time (ranging from a few hours to a few days for white blood cells, to about 10 days for platelets, to about 120 days for red blood cells) and must be replaced constantly. Certain conditions may trigger additional production of blood cells. When the oxygen content of body tissues is low or the number of red blood cells decreases, the kidneys produce and release erythropoietin, a hormone that stimulates the bone marrow to produce more red blood cells [4]. The bone marrow produces and releases more white blood cells in response to infections. To respond to bleeding, the bone marrow produces and releases more

platelets. Aging has some effect on bone marrow and blood cells, resulting in less cell-producing bone marrow. While this decrease generally does not cause problems, problems may arise when the body experiences an increased demand for blood cells: the bone marrow of an older adult may be less able to meet those increased demands. Anemia is the most common result.

Body tissues grow by increasing the number of cells. Cells in many tissues in the body divide and grow very quickly until we become adults. When we are adults many cells mature and become specialised for their particular job in the body. So they don't make copies of themselves (reproduce) so often. But some cells, such as skin cells or blood cells are dividing all the time. When cells become damaged or die the body makes new cells to replace them. This process is called cell division. So, a cell doubles by dividing into two. Two cells become four and so on. It seems that human cells can reproduce up to 50 or 60 times at most. Then they usually die. Stem cells provide a pool of dividing cells that the body uses to restock damaged or old cells. Stem cells are a kind of 'starter cell'. They have the potential to develop into different cell types in the body. When a stem cell multiplies, the resulting cells may remain as stem cells. But under the right conditions, they become a type of cell with a more specialised function. Stem cells occur in the body in various places and stages during our lifetime. When we are an embryo, developing in our mother's womb stem cells give rise to all the different tissues and organs of the body. In adults each type of stem cell is usually only able to develop into a few specific types of cell. For example, adult stem cells in the bone marrow, known as haematopoietic stem cells, usually only give rise to different types of blood cell.

Cancer stem cells- Scientists now believe that stem cells might play a role in the development of cancer. They think that some tumours develop from faulty stem cells. This has led to the idea of cancer stem cells, which scientists have now identified in a range of cancer types. The types include bowel, breast and prostate

cancer as well as leukaemia. Researchers are looking at whether some treatments could target cancer stem cells.

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted cells are the basic building blocks of all living things. The human body is composed of trillions of cells. They provide structure for the body, take in nutrients from food, convert those nutrients into energy, and carry out specialized functions. Cells also contain the body's hereditary material and can make copies of themselves. Cells have many parts, each with a different function. Some of these parts, called organelles, are specialized structures that perform certain tasks within the cell. Cells are the building blocks of the human body as our body is composed of trillions of cells. Cells provide structure to living organisms and help in the proper functioning of the body. There are a variety of cells in the human body that perform different functions such as brain cells helping in coordination, blood cells carrying oxygen throughout the body, etc. Some most important cells in the human body are nerve cells, blood cells (RBCs, WBCs, and platelets), stem cells, etc. Thus, almost all cells are equally important in the human body.

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